

JOURNAL OF DENTISTRY AND ALLIED SCIENCE

Volume: 04, No: 02

July, 2021

ISSN: 2791-0857

Peer Reviewed Journal

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(A Project of DMCR Foundation)

In Vitro Comparison of CBCT Imaging and Naked Eye Observation for Locating MB2 Canals in Extracted Permanent Maxillary first Molar

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Abstract:

Background: The accurate detection of root canal anatomy is essential for successful endodontic treatment. The use of cone-beam computed tomography (CBCT) imaging has been shown to improve the detection of additional MB canals. The study aimed to compare the accuracy of CBCT imaging and naked eye observation in detecting the presence of mesiobuccal (MB2) canal in extracted permanent maxillary first molar.

Methods: This study was conducted in a private clinic using extracted teeth from 118 Bangladeshi patients. The sample size consisted of permanent maxillary first molars only. After all aseptic precaution, the presence of canals was evaluated using CBCT imaging and naked eye observation. Then, the data were analyzed using descriptive statistics (frequency and percentage) and the McNemar's test was used to compare the presence or absence of MB2 canal between the CBCT and naked-eye examination methods which was significant at 5% level in 95% confidence interval ($p < 0.05$).

Results: The results showed that the mesiobuccal 2 canal was detected in 63.6% of teeth using CBCT imaging compared to 55.9% with naked eye observation which was statistically significant ($p < 0.001$).

Conclusion: The findings of this study suggest that the use of CBCT imaging may improve the detection of mesiobuccal 2 canal in permanent maxillary first molar compared to naked eye observation. However, naked eye observation remains a reliable method for detecting other canals.

Keywords: Maxillary molar, Second Mesiobuccal canal, Cone-beam computed tomography

Journal of Dentistry and Allied Science, Vol. 4 No 2
Article Received: 17 May 2021, Accepted: 21 Jun 2021

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Introduction:

The knowledge of the internal anatomy of the root canal system is essential to perform a successful root canal treatment. In the maxillary molars, the mesiobuccal root is the most challenging root to treat due to its complex internal anatomy. Studies have reported that the mesiobuccal root of maxillary molars frequently contains two canals, referred to as mesiobuccal 1 (MB1) and mesiobuccal 2 (MB2), and this complexity can lead to treatment failure.^{1,2} The identification and management of these canals have been identified as significant factors in the success of root canal treatment.³ The American Association of Endodontics (AAE) also recommends that clinicians should make every effort to identify all the canals during root canal treatment.⁴

Second Mesio buccal canals (MB2) in maxillary first molar are often unexploited during endodontic therapy and are a foremost reason of treatment failure. Its prevalence is known to vary among different populations and there is inadequate information on its prevalence in Bangladeshi population. In-depth and elaborate knowledge of the root canal anatomy of teeth plays a pivotal role in endodontic treatment. This is in essence true in teeth that exhibit intricacies and variations in their internal morphology like the maxillary molars.⁵ According to Vertucci FJ et. al Maxillary first molar is one of the most commonly treated teeth as it is the first teeth to erupt into the oral cavity.⁶ Along with largest pulp volume and have highest number of roots (mesiobuccal, distobuccal and palatal roots), variations in size, shape, form and internal anatomy of each canal, mesio buccal root shows the maximum variations.⁶ Witherspoon DE (2013) declared that 44% of retreatment in maxillary first molars is due to missed canals and 93% of these missed canals are identified in the mesiobuccal root. These missed canals in mesiobuccal roots are frequently a second mesiobuccal canal (MB2 canal), whose existence may be ascribed to the wide bucco-palatal dimensions of the mesiobuccal root. These accentuates that failure to detect, debride and obturate this canal can be a threat to success of endodontic therapy in maxillary first molar.⁷

The study aimed to compare the accuracy of CBCT imaging with naked-eye observation in the identification of MB2 canals in the mesiobuccal root of extracted maxillary permanent first molars. The findings of this study will provide valuable information to clinicians regarding the use of CBCT imaging in the identification of MB2 canals and aid in the success of root canal treatment in maxillary molars.

Methods

This study was designed as an in vitro study conducted in a private dental clinic in Bangladesh. The study population consisted of 118 extracted permanent maxillary molars, which were obtained from Bangladeshi citizens. The extracted teeth were obtained from patients who required dental extractions due to reasons such as caries, periodontal diseases, and orthodontic treatments. The teeth were collected over a period of 6 months and were stored in 1% thymol solution 1 week followed by 0.9% saline solution until the start of the study. The teeth were kept in a well-constructed container with a secure lid to prevent leaking during transport. The container was labeled with biohazard symbol. The teeth were numbered from 1 to 118. Twelve teeth were positioned and organized in a wax rim in a row (fig 1). The inclusion criteria for this study were maxillary permanent molars with fully formed roots and without any prior endodontic treatment. The exclusion criteria were teeth with root caries, root resorption, and teeth with root canal treatments. Radiographic Examination Cone-beam computed tomography (CBCT) and naked-eye examination (fig 2) were used to detect the presence of MB2 canal in the maxillary molars. An access cavity was prepared under Halogen bulbs using #2 and #4 Endo Access bur (Maillefer, Dentsply, Switzerland). Initial penetration was made in the exact center of the mesial pit, with the bur directed toward the palatal using a high-speed handpiece to the depth of dentin. The bur was directed toward the orifice of the palatal canal. When a drop was felt, the pulp chamber was reached. The larger palatal canal was located first after which safe-ended #0152 Endo-Z bur (Maillefer, Dentsply, Switzerland) was used, keeping it in contact with the floor of the pulp chamber and moved mesiobuccally to the center of the MB cusp. The MB canal was explored beneath the cusp tip, and the bur was moved distally and slightly palatally to locate the distobuccal canal orifice. A conventional triangular access was modified to a trapezoidal shape to improve access to the additional canals. Final finishing and funneling of cavity walls were done with Endo-Z fissure bur. After an adequate access cavity preparation, the contents of the pulp chamber were removed using an endodontic excavator and subsequent irrigation with a 2.5% sodium hypochlorite solution. The pulp chamber floor was explored using an endodontic explorer, DG-16 (Maillefer, Dentsply, Switzerland). Exploration of groove connecting the canal orifice was performed with the use of K-files #6, #8, or #10 (Mani, Japan). Prepared specimens were then explored for MB2 in the following sequence

Stage 1: Teeth were checked with naked eye (unaided vision) for second canal in the MB root with the help of explorer and then k-files #6 or #8, and Ethylene Diamine Tetra Acetic Acid was used to negotiate MB2 canal. If canal was not located by naked eye, samples will be subjected to stage 2.

Stage 2: A gutta percha cone was placed on the right side of the wax rim to identify in the CBCT image, later each rim was scanned with CBCT Ez3D-i, (Vatech, Korea). Resolution was 0.4x 0.4x 0.2mm, dimension 430 x430 x760pixel, 98kVp, 9mA, the voxel of 0.2 mm was used with an exposure of 16 min. The record of the number of canals and their variations was recorded.

Fig 1: Naked Eye Examination

Fig 2: Examined by CBCT imaging

Two independent examiners assessed the CBCT and naked-eye images to determine the presence or absence of MB2 canal. Then, the data were entered and analysis was performed using the IBM Statistical Package for Social Sciences (SPSS) version 25.0. The McNemar’s tests was used to compare the presence or absence of MB2 canal between the CBCT and naked-eye examination methods which was significant at 5% level in 95% confidence interval ($p < 0.05$). The patients who donated the extracted teeth provided written informed consent for the use of their teeth in this study. All procedures were conducted in accordance with the ethical standards of the Declaration of Helsinki.

Results

The result of a study that aimed to investigate the identification of the MB2 canal in permanent maxillary first molar using CBCT imaging and naked eye observation.

Table 1: Identification of the canal using naked eye observation and Cone beam computed tomography (CBCT) imaging

	Naked eye observation f (%)	CBCT f (%)	Significance p
MB2 canal			$p < .001$
Found	66 (55.9%)	75 (63.6%)	
Non found	52(44.1%)	43 (36.4%)	
Total	118 (100%)	118 (100%)	

CBCT= Cone beam computed tomography, MB=Mesiobuccal, DB=Distobuccal, P=Palatal, f= frequency, %=percentage, $p < 0.05$

According to the findings presented in table 1 and figure 3, out of a total of 118 cases, the MB2 canal was found in 75 cases (63.6%) using CBCT imaging, while only 66 cases (55.9%) were identified through naked eye observation. The difference in the success rate of identifying the canal between the two methods is statistically significant ($p < .001$). Specifically, CBCT imaging was more effective in identifying the MB2 canal than naked eye observation, as it had a higher success rate of detecting the canal.

Figure 3: Comparison of the identification of the mesio-buccal 2 canal in extracted maxillary molars using CBCT imaging and naked eye observation.

CBCT= Cone beam computed tomography, MB=Mesiobuccal, f= frequency, %=percentage, $p < 0.001$

Discussion

In this study, we investigated the identification of the MB2 canal using CBCT imaging and naked eye observation. The results showed that the use of CBCT imaging had a higher success rate in identifying the canal compared to naked eye observation. These findings suggest that CBCT imaging can be a valuable tool for identifying the MB2 canal in clinical settings as well as the use of CBCT imaging may provide a higher rate of success in identifying the MB2 canal compared to naked eye observation. Our findings are consistent with previous research where Harry et al.⁸ describes 68.5% MB2 in the Indonesian population in a study with a microscope and ultrasonic tips; Alrahabi et al.⁹ found 70.6% MB2 canal in the Saudi population in their study with CBCT and Touzi et al.¹⁰ used sectioning method for the detection of MB2 canal and found 75.67% in Tunisian population. Similarly, in clinical studies, many researchers found MB2 canal in 72% and 70%, respectively by DOM and ultrasonic.^{11,12} This may be due to the fact that CBCT provides a three-dimensional view of the tooth, which allows for more accurate and detailed identification of the canal system. Therefore, CBCT imaging can provide more accurate information about the internal anatomy of the tooth, which is critical for the success of endodontic treatment. Therefore, the use of CBCT imaging can help improve the quality of endodontic treatment and reduce the risk of treatment failure as it allows for the proper cleaning, shaping and obturation of the canal system, thus reducing the risk of treatment failure. Therefore, the use of CBCT imaging should be carefully considered, and its benefits and risks should be weighed against each other in each case. Moreover, the laboratory studies showed that there are higher frequency of MB2 canal when compared to in vivo study. The clearing technique, along with stereomicroscope, showed a higher frequency of MB2 canal in different populations. Naik et al.¹² found over 84% of maxillary first molars had MB2 canals in the south Indian population in his study using clearing technique and stereomicroscope. On the other hand, in a laboratory's clearing technique, Farhana et al.¹³ described 36% frequency of the MB2 canal in the Bangladeshi population, as reported by magnifying

glass instead of stereomicroscope, which seems to be one reason for the lower frequency of MB2. There can be distortion in the morphology of the tooth as a result of the demineralization process. Moreover, the dyeing solution may not fully infiltrate into narrow canals and ramifications if the dimension is below the grain size of the injected dye.¹¹ This might also explain the reason for the lower frequency of MB2 in the study of Chowdhury et al.¹⁴ Sageer Ahmed et al.¹⁵ used A combination of ultrasonic, magnification, and RVG and described 68.6% and 72.2% MB2 canals in the maxillary right and left quadrant of Bangladeshi population.

Conclusion:

CBCT imaging is more effective in detecting mesiobuccal 2 canals in extracted maxillary permanent teeth compared to naked eye observation. These findings have important clinical implications for endodontic treatment planning and underscore the importance of using advanced imaging techniques such as CBCT to improve the accuracy of canal detection. However, further studies are needed to investigate the prevalence and distribution of MB2 canals in vivo, as well as the factors that may influence their identification and treatment to confirm the generalizability of these findings to a larger population for assessing the impact of CBCT imaging on treatment outcomes.

Limitations of the study

It is important to note that this study has some limitations. Firstly, the sample size was relatively small, which may limit the generalizability of the results. Secondly, the study was conducted in vitro using extracted teeth, which may not accurately reflect the clinical situation. As well as is possible that factors such as the age of the patient could affect the results.

Acknowledgement:

I wish to express my sincere gratitude to Dr. Md. Toufiqur Rahman and Dr. Sharmin Jahan for rendering help during this work.

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